

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D2.2 Final report on Data Harmonization

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interpretable, Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
ICUD	International Conference on Urban Drainage
IWGDM	International Working Group on Data and Models
JRA	Joint Research Activity
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RI	Research Infrastructure
SI	International System of Units
TA	Transnational Access
UCUM	Unified Code for Units of Measure
UDMT	Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems
WOLL	Water-Oriented Living Labs
WP	Work Package
XLSX	Microsoft Excel
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive summary

This deliverable (D2.2) is the final deliverable of Task2.1, which focuses on three main objectives: assessing harmonization needs within the consortium, exploring solutions to challenges, and evaluating the urban drainage community's broader needs. In agreement with the Water4All Partnership, which is analysing needs for data harmonization in the Water sector – we adjusted our strategic goals for this reporting period to three strategic areas: i) develop data harmonization concepts and standards, work on ii) implementations to facilitate the practical application of the concepts and, iii) establishing promoting best practices for data sharing and re-use in the Urban Drainage System (UDS) community.

In the first reporting period, a core consortium was established to guide harmonisation efforts. The group met monthly to evaluate progress, ensure alignment, and maintain momentum toward achieving the work package goals. The consortium identified Zenodo as the primary platform for data sharing, based on its open-access nature, automatic DOI assignment, support for a variety of content types, and long-term data preservation capabilities. Additionally, a simplified Data Management Plan (DMP) template was developed, incorporating feedback from researchers and addressing issues such as licensing to ensure improved data accessibility.

The second reporting period focused on advancing three key areas of WP2:

Development of data harmonisation concepts and standards: A thorough review of existing Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) glossaries, vocabularies, and established standards/ontologies (e.g., INSPIRE, OGC, ISO, SSN/SOSA, GEMET, and EnvThes) was conducted. This review provided the foundation for developing a controlled vocabulary tailored for Co-UDlabs, which will serve as the basis for a new ontology designed to meet the urban drainage community's specific needs.

Implementation of corresponding tools: To facilitate data sharing and reproducible workflows, the project adopted platforms such as Zenodo, OpenAIRE, and Renku. Furthermore, the integration of OGC standards, such as the SensorThings API, enabled real-time data sharing of WOLL-type data, enhancing the exchange of up-to-date information across the consortium.

Promotion of best practices for FAIR data and reproducible research: The WP2 team actively engaged in knowledge exchange and dissemination. Notable efforts included presenting findings at the International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD) 2024, organizing a collaborative exchange at the University of La Coruña, and contributing educational materials to the European Junior Scientist Workshop 2024 to foster a collaborative environment for data sharing and harmonisation in the urban drainage community.

WP2's outcomes significantly contribute to the Co-UDlabs project by promoting collaboration and transparency between research infrastructures and the urban drainage community. It has established a robust research infrastructure **supporting the European Open Science Cloud, enabling open science and seamless data sharing**, which are crucial for advancing urban drainage research. These efforts align with EU policies on open science, data spaces, and sustainable urban development.

1. Ensuring interoperability of Urban Drainage System Monitoring Data

1.1. Objectives and scope of the harmonization efforts

Within WP2 of the Co-UDLabs project, we have outlined three primary objectives:

O1: Assessment of Harmonization Requirements within the Consortium: Our first objective is to assess the essential prerequisites for achieving harmonization within our consortium. This involves determining the critical factors necessary to ensure that our data adheres to the FAIR principles, thereby facilitating accessibility and usability. Also, we need to identify a common data sharing platform.

O2: Investigation of Remedies for Identified Challenges: Our second objective revolves around investigating potential solutions for the challenges we uncover. On the one hand, this includes exploring the adoption of standardized protocols, methods, and technologies as remedies for the issues we encounter. On the other hand, this also requires identifying suitable tools to transform data into sharable formats, as well as sharing workflows and data versioning/provenance methods.

O3: Community-Wide Harmonization Assessment: Our third objective extends beyond the consortium and seeks to assess the harmonization needs of the broader urban drainage community, e.g., through coordinating with the IWA/IAHR International Working Group of Data and Models (IWGDM). This broader perspective aims to identify and address harmonization requirements at a community-wide level.

1.2. Results achieved in the first Reporting Period

Based on these objectives, the main achievements in the reporting period were:

- **A core consortium has been formed to guide harmonisation efforts:** The establishment of a core consortium dedicated to guiding harmonisation efforts, meeting monthly to assess progress and maintain alignment, consolidated the project's commitment to a structured and collaborative approach to data interoperability. This core group of all partners involved in WP2 played a crucial role in facilitating data sharing by establishing guidelines and revising templates, such as the Data Management Plan (DMP) and deciding on where to best put the sparse resources.
- **Selecting Zenodo as the main data sharing platform:** Zenodo was selected as the primary data sharing platform for Co-UDLabs because it is an open-access repository that offers robust features such as automatic DOI assignment, support for a wide range of content types, and long-term data preservation. We implemented a so-called “community” for Co-UDLabs resources which is curated by UDC as the Principal Investigator. This not only concerns datasets, but also reports and various other types of data Figure 1.
- **Suggestions for a revised Data Management Plan (DMP) and standards:** Based on the findings from Transnational Access (TA) and Joint Research Activities (JRA), we developed suggestions for a more relevant DMP. This included simplifications, less details and incorporating feedback from researchers and addressing issues related to licensing for improved data accessibility. We also suggested to use OGC interoperability standards and to investigate existing Ontologies for UDS as a basis for data models and data sharing formats.

2. Establishing Core Governance, Refining Data Management and selecting a Data Sharing Infrastructure

This section highlights the main achievements in the second phase after the project, specifically focusing on core governance among the partners and in the urban drainage community, which is important for continuity of data sharing after the end of Co-UDLabs. Also, we describe the evolution of our Data Management Plan (DMP), and the selection of Zenodo as our primary data sharing infrastructure. For a detailed breakdown, please refer to the main reporting document (Anta et al., 2022).

2.1. Governance Establishment: during the Co-UDLabs project and beyond

The core group of WP2 (as detailed in Deliverable 2.1) serves as the main governance body within Co-UDLabs. This group continues to meet regularly, having held over 20 meetings to date, ensuring the effective coordination of data harmonisation tasks. These meetings provide strategic direction for WP2 and include all project partners, fostering effective information exchange and collaboration.

The governance framework is now expanding to integrate specialized expertise, particularly in the development of an ontology for the Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) community. This initiative aims to strengthen semantic consistency and enhance data models, ensuring that the data produced is interoperable and standardized across various systems and platforms.

In Co-UDLabs, we identified two primary types of data:

- 1) **Individual Laboratory Data:** This dataset is generated from laboratory setups with common sensors, such as water level monitors or flow meters, as well as specialized equipment like hyperspectral cameras or in-house developments, such as the FSB pipe mapping instrument (see Deliverable 6.2). This type of data, typical of INFRAIA groups, requires agreement among the Research Infrastructures (RIs) to ensure reproducibility and future reusability of experiments.
- 2) **Data from Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLL):** This includes data from real-world systems, such as the Urban Water Observatory (UWO) or operational sewer systems. This data is essential for supporting a paradigm shift in urban drainage management across Europe, particularly in the context of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), which emphasizes evidence-based UDS management (see Deliverable 2.5). This directive calls for monitoring by 2030 and using data in compliance assessments, integrated drainage planning, and the development of "digital tools". These datasets are critical not only for local and national regulators but also for establishing Performance Indicators for the European Commission.

Therefore, the data harmonization efforts within Co-UDLabs have significant long-term implications beyond the project's conclusion. Developing common data standards will need to continue, particularly for Water-Oriented Living Lab (WOLL)-type datasets. To address this, we initiated a process to discuss our data harmonization and interoperability results with the broader UDS community, with a particular focus on the development of ontologies.

Although there is no formal international governance institution for UDS, organizations like the *International Water Association (IWA)* or *International Association for Hydro-Environment Engineering and Research (IAHR)* could play a key role in organizing future harmonization efforts. This would be similar to the work of the IWA working group

MetaCo (Villez & et al., 2024).¹ The primary governance body for the UDS research community is the *IWA/IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage*, which structures its work through voluntary committees known as working groups. Under the JCUD, the **International Working Group on Data and Models (IWGDM)** is the relevant group for facilitating discussions on data sharing and harmonization (IWA: <https://iwa-network.org/>; IAHR: <https://www.iahr.org/>; JCUD: <https://jicud.org/>).

One of the key outcomes of Co-UDlabs' governance strategy is therefore the initiation of activities in collaboration with the IWGDM (see Section 3.1.3.). This collaboration ensures that the efforts around data sharing and harmonization extend beyond the project's duration and contribute to the ongoing development of standardized practices within the global UDS community.

2.2. The Data Management Plan (DMP)

The Data Management Plan (DMP) was revised during this reporting period to facilitate its adoption across researchers. Based on feedback from discussions, including the visit to the University of La Coruña, we reviewed the existing structure and developed a simplified template. This revised template reflects the feedback and can be accessed in the Annex to the project report.

The core data collection processes for Transnational Access (TAs) and Joint Research Activities (JRAs) remain unchanged, only the way the questions are framed has been updated. To better capture the details of each project data management practices, we choose to allow open-text fields instead of standardized responses, leaving WP2 responsible to handle and compare the entries across projects. Further, the issue of licensing within the DMP, as discussed in Deliverable 2.1, has been resolved with the adoption of the CC0 license for data sharing. This decision, now incorporated into the project report, improves accessibility to the datasets and removes legal barriers for reusing data, both for new or existing submissions.

As we worked implementing these updates, we describe the lessons learned from the process. First, the DMP is proving to be more than just a compliance requirement, it is becoming a core tool for advancing open science. A functional DMP not only manage data, it can link datasets to publications via Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), increasing its utility as a central guide for research.

To develop its full potential, the DMP could evolve into a living document that integrates data, datasets and publications. Machine Actionable DMPs (maDMPs) take the DMP concept further by using Persistent Identifiers (PID) services to connect all resources associated with a DMP. A data management plan should not be treated as an administrative task for which standardized text can be pasted from model templates, with no intention to implement the planned measures early on (Miksa et al., 2019). This new system aims to reduce the burden on researchers by generating automated updates to a plan and facilitating the integration with systems that support research.

While the DMP is a requirement for all TA and JRA projects, completing it remains challenging for some UDS researchers. Despite simplifying the template, researchers often delay filling out the DMP or provide incomplete information. We also identify inconsistencies in the way researchers describe their data, some researchers provide detailed descriptions, while others give vague input. These differences complicate the process to consolidate and compare inputs across the project.

¹ Online at: <https://iwa-network.org/groups/meta-data-collection-and-organization-metaco/>.

After the second TA call, we made substantial progress in collecting DMPs from partner institutions (Table 1). However, submissions on time remains a challenge, as the responsibility lies with the project team, who usually are newly formed groups who do not have a long history of collaboration. Another issue we identified is maintaining up to date the datasets linked to publications in the DMP after the project conclusion. Currently, this process is manual, but we are exploring solutions like automatic DOI-based updates.

Adopting a tool like DMP Online, which offers a more structured solution for data management, was recommended but not embraced due to its complexity and lack of guidance for researchers. We currently rely on simpler methods such as MSWord files, which are accessible but still lack the functionality of DMP Online. The future work is focus on providing the additional training and support of the platform for better adoption. These lessons are driving improvements in data management processes, including consistent data entry and exploring automated updates

Table 1 DMP collection data from TAs

<i>RI</i>	<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Variables Names</i>	<i>#</i>	<i>Sensors Names</i>	<i>#</i>
<i>A/B FLUME</i>	Mignot	2023	Flow Depths, Flow pressure, Solute concentration, Velocity	4	Depth Sensor, Flow Meter, Fluorometer, Laser Doppler Velocimetry, Particle Image Velocimetry, Planar Concentration Analysis System, Pressure Sensor	7
<i>ANNULAR</i>	Regueiro	2023	Conductivity, Density, Depth, Digital PCR, Dissolved Oxygen, Flow Rate, Flow velocity, Mean grain size, Metagenomics, pH, q-PCR, Temperature, Thermal conductivity, Velocity, Volumetric heat capacity	15	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler, Conductivity Sensor, Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy, Depth Sensor, Dissolved Oxygen Sensor, Flow Cytometry, Image based particle tracking, Microscopy and imaging facilities, Molecular Method, Particle Image Tomography, Particle Image Velocimetry, pH Sensor, Scanning Electron Microscopy, Sediment Analysis, Temperature Sensor	15
<i>ANNULAR</i>	Morato	2023	CRISPR-Cas, Microbiological analysis, Physicalchemical analysis	3	Molecular Method, Water and Soil Sample Analysis	2
<i>BENS</i>	Peña	2023	Chemical Oxygen Demand, Conductivity, Flow Rate, Total Nitrogen, Total Phosphorus, Total Solids, Total Suspended Solids, Turbidity, Velocity, Water level	10	Computer Vision System, Conductivity Sensor, Flow Meter, Level Sensor, Turbidity Sensor, Ultrasonic Flow Transducer, Velocity Profiler, Wastewater Sample Analysis	8
<i>BENS</i>	Regueiro	2023	Density, Mean grain size, Moisture content, Organic matter, Porosity, Temperature	6	Sediment Analysis, Temperature Sensor	2
<i>BLOCK</i>	COUPE	2024	Biomass, Conductivity, Microbial concentrations, pH, Ryegrass germination, Ryegrass growth Rate	6	Conductivity Sensor, Image analysis, Lab analysis, pH Sensor	4
<i>BLOCK</i>	Franca	2024	Density, Depth, Flow Rate, Rainfall, Temperature, Velocity	6	Flow Sensor, PTV, Rain Gauge, Sediment Analysis, Temperature Sensor, UDV profiler, Water depth sensor	7
<i>BURIED</i>	Li	2023	Conductivity, Flow pressure, Flow Rate, Flow velocity, Quantities and particle sizes of sediments, Solute concentration, Temperature, Velocity, Water level	9	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler, Calibrated Weirs, Conductivity Sensor, Flow Meter, Laser Doppler Velocimetry, Particle Image Velocimetry, Pressure Sensor, Solute Concentration Sensor, Temperature Sensor, Water Level Wave Probes, Weighing Scale	11
<i>HALL</i>	Bares	2023	Ammonium Nitrogen, Chemical Oxygen Demand, Orthophosphate Phosphorus, Turbidity, Velocity	5	Lagrangian Sensor Platform, Multispectral and Hyperspectral Sensors, Turbidity Sensor, Ultrasonic Profilers	4
<i>HALL</i>	Langefeld	2023	Density, Moisture content, Organic matter, Temperature, Thermal conductivity, Volumetric heat capacity, Volumetric moisture content	7	Dynamic Heat Pulse System, Sediment Analysis, Temperature Sensor	3

<i>IKT LTF</i>	Beenen	2023	Flow Rate, Pressure, Simulation damages, Water leak	4	CCTV, Flow Meter, Leak Tightness Testing, Pressure Sensor, Pump	5
<i>IKT LTF</i>	Verhulst	2023	Strain	1	Strain Gauges	1
<i>IKT TEST</i>	JRA3	2023	Fine-grained and coarse-grained, filterable mineral substances, Flow Rate, Mineral oil hydrocarbons, Polyethylene and polystyrene, Waste water (synthetic), Water level	6	Flow Meter, Pressure Sensor, Retention Testing, Simulation, Weighing Scale	5
<i>RTC</i>	GUTIERREZ	2024	Flow Rate, Velocity, Water level	3	Conductance probes, Flowmeter, Particle Image, Velocimetry, Radar sensor	4
<i>RTC</i>	Van der Werf	2024	Flow Rate, Water level	2	Flow Sensor, Water level sensor	2
<i>STREET</i>	Lutze	2024	Conductivity, DOC, Flow Rate, MCPA, Moisture content, pH, Rainfall, Temperature, Titanium, UV light intensity	10	Conductivity Sensor, Environmental Sensor, Flow Sensor, Flowmeter, ICP/MS, Lab analysis, LC/MS-MS, pH Sensor, Rain Gauge, Temperature Sensor, UV Light meter	11
<i>STREET</i>	Linnemann	2024	Conductivity, Mean grain size, Rainfall, Rainfall duration, Sediment concentration, Temperature, Water level, Water volume, Water weight	9	Conductivity Sensor, Depth Sensor, Flow Sensor, PSD Analysis, Rain Gauge, Sediment Analysis, Temperature Sensor, Weighing Scale	8
<i>UWO</i>	Dittmer	2023	Conductivity, Flow Rate, Humidity, Pressure, Rainfall, Solar radiation, Temperature, Water level, Wind	9	Correlation Wedge Sensors, Dielectric Conductivity Sensors, Dual Sensors, Multi-Parameter Weather Station, Non-Contact Radar Flow Meters, Overflow Structure Instrumentation, Rain Gauge	7
<i>UWO</i>	Abdelaal	2024	Hydrogen Sulfide, Temperature	2	SulfiLogger probe	1
<i>UWO</i>	Dittmer	2024	Catchment area, Rainfall, Water level	3	Image analysis, Overflow Structure Instrumentation, Radar data, Rain Gauge	4

2.3. Selection of Zenodo as Data Sharing Infrastructure

For the Co-UDlabs project, Zenodo was chosen as the main data-sharing infrastructure (Figure 1), following an analysis described in the first deliverable of WP2. This open-access platform, managed by CERN, is broadly trusted in the scientific community for sharing data and publications. Zenodo offers several advantages, including the automatic assignment of DOI for all uploaded content, the support of a wide selection of content types, and long-term data preservation, which is especially suitable for projects like CoUDLabs that want to ensure that data remains accessible long after the project finishes.

However, Zenodo has certain limitations, which needs to be addressed. It does not enforce strict metadata guidelines, leaving users to manually assign metadata and keywords which can result in datasets with inconsistent descriptions and reduced discoverability. As a repository, Zenodo is great for preserving static outputs, but is not designed to handle real-time data, which limits its application for monitoring Urban Drainage Systems. Future projects involving streaming data should consider complementary tools, such as OGC SensorThings API, to meet the demands of real-time data sharing.

Moving forward we addressed some of the platform limitations to maximize its utility for Co-UDlabs. One step was (and will be) the introduction of standardized keywords with predefined categories making the datasets easier to find. Also, already today, data stored on Zenodo are directly visible in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) because Zenodo is integrated with the EOSC ecosystem (Figure 2). By being visible in EOSC, data hosted on Zenodo become part of a wider network that is accessible to researchers, policymakers, and institutions across Europe and beyond. This increases the reach and discoverability of the data, ensuring that it can be easily found by others. The reusability must still be improved by internationally recognized ontologies, data models and exchange formats.

Looking after the project conclusion in 2025, the Co-UDlabs community on Zenodo could evolve into a larger community, possibly as part of the IWGDM (see below).

Figure 1: Co-UDlabs community on Zenodo, including the current set of “Subjects”, i.e. keywords, which describe the datasets. These will most probably be harmonized to the final set of attributes until May 2025.

The screenshot shows the European Open Science Cloud (EU Node) website. The browser address bar displays the URL: [https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/data?q="](https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/data?q=). The page header includes the European Commission logo and a navigation menu with items: Home, About, Services, Resource Hub, Support, Contributors, News & Events, and User Space. The main content area is titled "Resource hub" and features a search bar with the query "CoUDLabs". Below the search bar, there are tabs for "All resources", "Publications", "Data", "Software", "Other Products", "Services", "Data Sources", "Training", "Interoperability Guidelines", and "Tools". The "Data" tab is selected, and the results show "Showing 1 to 11 of 11 resources". A filter sidebar on the left includes options for "Access right", "Document type", "Publication date", and "Funder". A "Dataset (11)" checkbox is checked. A "Relevance" dropdown menu is visible. The first result is a dataset titled "CoUDLabs_WP8_T831_AaU_001 Application of Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) technique in Aalborg retention pond". The dataset is categorized as "DATA" and "OPEN ACCESS". It has a year of 2023, 0 views, 0 downloads, and 0 citations. A brief description states: "This dataset includes the data obtained during the installation of a camera system to determine the surface".

Figure 2: Co-UDlabs FAIR data in the European Open Science Cloud (Access Date: 12.12.2024). Given the lack of data models, it is currently only possible to find the data through keyword search. Co-UDLabs and CoUDLabs will lead to different results and the data are not easily Interoperable and Reusable.

3. Standardize Data Practices and Enhance Data Interoperability

In the previous deliverable, we identified challenges in harmonizing data practices across Research Infrastructures (RI) and Transnational Access (TA) projects, including inconsistent terminology and unit standards, which complicate data interoperability. Enabling researchers to interpret and share data across projects allows them to develop reliable models for urban water challenges.

Building on lessons from meetings with the [Water4all](#) project,² this section is reorganized to follow a structured approach for advancing data interoperability in Urban Drainage Systems (UDS): Concept Development, Implementation, and Teaching/Dissemination (Tikansak & Dissing, 2024). By addressing each phase, WP2 aims to create a harmonized framework to engage the community in FAIR data practices and improve the usability of datasets. A common framework for data collection, storage, and sharing ensures that datasets are comparable

² Analysis based on personal communications from and collaboration with Sylvain Grellet and Henrik Dissing.

across regions, research projects, and platforms. This includes using terminologies, measurement units, and data formats that are universally understood, regardless of the source or methodology.

3.1. Develop concepts

Ontologies and data models play a critical role in building a harmonised framework. Ontologies provide a structured vocabulary for key concepts, variables, and relationships within the field, while data models define how these concepts are represented and interconnected. Collaborations with experts in knowledge representation, such as Ana-Claudia Sima (Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics) and Luís Moreira de Sousa (Instituto Superior Técnico, University of Lisbon), have helped understand the requirements and first steps into building an ontology. We started gathering the requirements for building an ontology in the urban drainage systems field. Our approach first focus on reusing existing frameworks and aligning with European and international standards. These standards provide structured vocabularies and relationships that guide data interpretation, building the semantic consistency.

Building this ontology requires a collaborative and iterative process. It requires engaging stakeholders, appointing a dedicated project leader to coordinate efforts, and hosting iterative workshops to build consensus on the concepts. This approach emphasizes practical data management by prioritizing datasets over abstract models. Starting with tabular data (e.g., CSV files), relationships can then be developed progressively from simple relational databases to more sophisticated Knowledge Graphs, ensuring the ontology evolves logically and is adaptable to real-world needs.

3.1.1. Determining domain and scope of ontology

Developing an ontology begins with addressing questions that guide its scope. What domain should the ontology cover, and how can it support data harmonization efforts? What types of questions should the ontology answer, particularly in relation to monitoring systems, infrastructure, and variables? Finally, who will use and maintain the ontology to keep it relevant over time? These considerations will create a robust framework that meets the needs of the UDS ontology (Noy, 2001).

For Co-UDlabs, the domain of the ontology is Monitoring in the Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) field, encompassing lab-scale and WOLL-type UDS data (Section 2.1). This domain aligns with the project's broader goal of enhancing data harmonization within UDS research (Section 4). By acting as a structured reference for knowledge organization, it will support researchers, policymakers, and practitioners in standardizing data related to monitoring sensors, variables, infrastructure, and units in the UDS field.

The ontology address questions in the context of monitoring. It identifies the key variables and sensors involved, clarify how these variables are measured, and standardize the units employed. Additionally, it should map the relationships between specific infrastructure elements and their associated monitoring tasks.

Its users extend beyond the academic research community. Researchers in the UDS community will benefit from this ontology as a reference for project development, while urban drainage system managers such as e.g. water utilities, municipalities and water companies, can use it for policy development.

Our core results concern analysing existing reference standards and ontologies and develop a strategy towards an internationally recognized ontology and data sharing concept.

3.1.2. Analysis of existing reference standards and ontologies

Many well-established frameworks already provide robust foundations for monitoring water quality. By refining and extending these sources, we reduce duplication of effort. For our domain, key resources include INSPIRE, OGC, ISO standards, and SSN/SOSA ontologies.

INSPIRE Framework

The INSPIRE initiative³ offers a comprehensive framework for geospatial data interoperability across Europe, making it a cornerstone for developing the UDS ontology. Specifically, INSPIRE provides detailed schemas for utility and government services, with technical specifications for sewer and water networks (Table 2). These schemas, accessible through INSPIRE's technical guidelines and GitHub repository, include attributes and relationships that align well with the UDS field networks (INSPIRE Data Specification on Utility and Government Services – Technical Guidelines, 2024).

Table 2 INSPIRE application schema register

Environmental Management Facilities	us-emf
Common Utility Network Elements	us-net-common
Sewer Network	us-net-sw
Water Network	us-net-wa

A single standard cannot address all aspects of infrastructure and monitoring, therefore, combining complementary standards allows for a more holistic approach. While INSPIRE focuses on static geospatial objects, such as pipes and manholes, SSN/SOSA ontologies add a dynamic layer for modelling sensors and their observations over time. This combination bridges the gap between infrastructure representation and real-time monitoring. For instance, incorporating SSN/SOSA could enrich an INSPIRE dataset of a sewer network with real-time flow rates or water quality measurements from embedded sensors. Additionally, INSPIRE extends OGC standards to accommodate European-specific requirements, ensuring compatibility while addressing the unique needs of infrastructure and environmental data sharing.

SSN/SOSA Framework

Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN) and Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontologies are frameworks that enable the representation of sensor networks, observations, sampling and actuations, which are highly relevant for monitoring in Urban Drainage Systems (UDS). By providing a structured way to describe sensors, observations, and their relationships, SSN/SOSA help model complex data environments. These ontologies are applied in fields like environmental monitoring, smart city applications, and the Internet of Things (IoT), all of which intersect with UDS real-time monitoring needs.

The two frameworks work together seamlessly, but they have different purposes and levels of complexity. SSN is an ontology that provides a detailed framework for describing sensor networks, the devices, observations, interactions, and platforms. SOSA is an ontology focusing on the core elements: sensors, observations, actuators, and samples. SOSA is often used for simple real-time IoT systems, while SSN and its capabilities are more used for

³ Online at: https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/index_en.

environmental monitoring. SOSA forms the core module of SSN, providing the basic concepts that SSN expands with additional metadata.

SSN/SOSA ontologies complement other standards, such as INSPIRE and OGC's Observations and Measurements (O&M). While INSPIRE focuses on static geospatial objects like pipes and manholes, SSN/SOSA add a dynamic layer by modeling sensors and their observations over time. This integration bridges infrastructure representation and real-time monitoring, enabling richer datasets. For instance, INSPIRE datasets describing sewer networks can be enriched with SSN/SOSA models to include real-time flow rates or water quality metrics.

SSN and SOSA are Web Ontology Language (OWL) while O&M is a Unified Modeling Language (UML). The Web Ontology Language (OWL) is used for creating semantic web models, while the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a framework for software and data modeling. UML focuses on structuring data models but lacks the semantic capabilities of OWL. The transformation from O&M's UML-based structure to SSN/SOSA's OWL-based framework is needed for semantic web applications. This process translates UML classes (e.g., OM_Observation) into OWL equivalents (e.g., sosa:Observation), along with the relationships and properties.

The alignment between SOSA and OM is needed for interoperability between the systems, and explained in section 6.3.4 of the SOSA documentation. It provides a basis for transforming OM-XML data into RDF resources or OWL individuals according to the SOSA/SSN ontologies. The primary classes from OM have direct equivalents in SOSA classes.

GWSW Ontology

The Urban Water Data Dictionary ('GegevensWoordenboek Stedelijk Water' - GWSW) is an ontology designed for urban water management in the Netherlands, providing a framework to describe systems and processes within the field. Developed and managed by the RIONED Foundation, the GWSW is an open standard which is mandatory for the Netherlands. Built on linked data principles, it is part of the Semantic Web and modelled in RDF, RDFS, and OWL-2.

To adapt the GWSW ontology for Urban Drainage Systems (UDS), we translated its terms into English and filter them to the needs of UDS (Figure 3). This process involved adding `rdfs:label [language:en]` and `skos:definition [language:en]`⁴ for each concept, ensuring the usability of the ontology for an international audience. The finalized ontology was exported as a .ttl (Turtle) file, compatible with the semantic framework.

⁴ RDFS (Resource Description Framework Schema), SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System).

Figure 3: Translation of classes from Dutch to English of the GWSW ontology displayed as a .ttl file in the open software Protege (Source: Chavarria, 2024).

The adaptation process included analysing the references to European Standards for wastewater engineering and urban drainage. These standards are the sources for the majority of terms in the GWSW ontology (EN 16323, 2014; EN 752:2017, 2017; EN 13508-2, 2011; EN 13508-1, 2012; EN 16932-1, 2018; NEN 3610:2022 NI, 2022). This approach validate that the ontology aligns with recognized concepts, improving its interoperability. The references include:

- EN 16323:2014 (replaces EN 1085:2007 and NEN 3300:1996): Glossary of wastewater engineering terms.
- EN 752:2017: Drain and sewer systems outside buildings - Sewer system management.
- DIN EN 13508-2:2011-08: Investigation and assessment of drain and sewer systems outside buildings – Part 2: Visual inspection coding system
- EN 13508-1:2012 (replaces NEN 3398:2015 and NEN 3398:2004): Investigation and assessment of drain and sewer systems outside buildings – Part 1: General requirements
- EN 16932:2018: Standards for drain and sewer management and cleaning.
- NEN 3610:2022 nl: Basic geoinformation model for Earth-related spatial objects.

Thesaurus: GEMET and EnvThes

The ISO 25964 defines thesaurus as a controlled and structured vocabulary that organizes concepts through hierarchical and associative relationships, also establishes intra and interlinguistic equivalence relationships between terms representing these concepts in the same language or different languages (ISO 25964-1:2011, 2011). The General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET), developed by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet), is used as a resource for metadata enrichment in different environmental fields. GEMET supports standardized vocabulary in the field of water quality monitoring.

EnvThes is a European thesaurus developed within the LTER-Europe (Long-Term Ecosystem Research in Europe) network, with its creation initiated through the EnvEurope and ExpeER projects in 2014. The resource has been designed to address the metadata and semantic needs of environmental research datasets, particularly in alignment with INSPIRE Directive themes.

3.1.3. Towards an internationally recognized ontology for UDS monitoring data

As mentioned above, we initiated the process to discuss data harmonization with the IWGDM. The original plan was to initiate specialized meetings in late 2024, but this has been rescheduled to mid-January 2025. The monthly sessions will run through April and follow a structured format allocating 20 minutes for expert input, 20 minutes for open discussion, and 20 minutes to outline next steps. The proposed breakout topics for the group include laboratory data management and streaming data, which is especially important for real-world applications, e.g. support future EU-data spaces on water with routine data or future compliance assessment in the scope of Annex V of the UWWTD. To assemble a team of at least 10 experts, we set up a registration portal on the Co-UDlabs website,⁵ with outreach via platforms like LinkedIn and direct invitations to experts in the field, e.g. from Water4all, the Wataverse project, the STREAM network, etc.

As our skills regarding semantic web concepts are limited, we will join forces with the Computer Science Department of the Instituto Superior Técnico of the University of Lisbon, who are experienced with ontology processes. Our expert group will provide feedback on the ontology development and focus on knowledge organization. Our intention is to disseminate our results with a workshop at the Urban Drainage Modelling Conference 2025, organized by the IWGDM in Innsbruck, Austria, presenting our conclusions from our data harmonization efforts and discuss next steps towards developing an internationally recognized Ontology, data models and formats. We aim to integrate current developments, such as relevant EU data spaces^{6,7} or the UK STREAM Water data.⁸

Looking ahead, the IWGDM could establish itself as a reference in urban drainage data management by implementing FAIR strategies for UDS data. Setting clear guidelines on how to describe, categorize, and tag UDS datasets to improve discoverability. Annual calls for datasets, shared on accessible platforms, can help build a base for a central repository of high-quality data, possibly in a data space on SmartCities.

Finally, aligning with global initiatives like STREAM or European data spaces can extend the impact, making urban drainage data interoperable across other disciplines. Role models for research-oriented data could be the Materials Cloud⁹ and for WOLL or utility data the European Language Grid (EGL),¹⁰ which host data and models and provide APIs to provide structured access to the data.

3.2. Collating and Categorizing Data Management Insights from Co-UDlabs Research Infrastructures

Developing robust concepts is the first step for asserting interoperability. Recognizing the need for consistent naming conventions, we did a review of UDS glossaries and vocabulary resources. We aligned the data outputs of Co-UDlabs with internationally recognized standards, including W3C SOSA/SSN, WaterML, and INSPIRE. Through

⁵ Accessible online at this link: <https://co-udlabs.eu/dissemination/event-directory/>.

⁶ See: <https://dssc.eu/space/DC/27983886/Community+of+Practice>.

⁷ Online at: <https://www.ds4sscc.eu/>.

⁸ See: <https://www.streamwaterdata.co.uk/>.

⁹ See: <https://www.materialscloud.org/home>.

¹⁰ Online at this link: <https://live.european-language-grid.eu/catalogue/>.

this alignment, we have a controlled vocabulary that serves as a reference within the TA projects (Figure 4). This vocabulary harmonizes variable names, sensor descriptors, monitoring vocabulary and definitions, improving data interoperability across the TA projects. This vocabulary will most probably serve as a basis of a future ontology that supports references for monitoring data and ensures the project contributions to the broader UDS community.

Figure 4 Sunburst chart representing the categorization of measurements within Co-UDlabs RIs. The core shows the RIs, followed by categories and specific variables in the outer layer. An interactive version can be accessed online [link]. (Source: Chavarría, 2024)

Mapping project variables to established data models can improve data interoperability. This process aligns variables collected across Transnational Access (TA) projects and Research Infrastructures (RI) with internationally recognized standards, uncovering gaps.

The process began by compiling a comprehensive list of variables from sensors, variables, and expert input. These were categorized into thematic groups, such as rainfall, hydraulics, and water quality, to facilitate systematic mapping. Using tools like Protégé and Python scripts, the variables were compared against established ontologies and standards, including W3C SOSA/SSN, WaterML, and INSPIRE. Many variables successfully aligned with existing representations, while others do not have counterparts in the standard ontologies.

This exercise shows usefulness and limitations of current frameworks. The unmatched variables reflect the need to extend the ontology to cover this unique data. Addressing these gaps support a more robust data model for the urban drainage community.

To communicate the results, visualizations such as Figure 4 and Figure 5 were created, illustrating the proportion of aligned variables versus those requiring further development. These visualizations can be made available on the project website in an interactive format, encouraging stakeholders to explore the relationships between variables and existing models. This approach fosters transparency and invites feedback, enriching the collective effort.

Figure 5: Sankey chart representing the mapping from references to TA and JRA variables categories. An interactive version can be accessed online [link]. [Source: Chavarría, 2024]

3.3. Provide implementations and tools

The exchange with the Water4all project emphasized that the application of concepts needs effective tools to advance data sharing and re-use. Co-UDlabs has adopted platforms like Zenodo and OpenAIRE for data sharing and RENKU for reproducible workflows. These tools address key challenges such as long-term data preservation, open-access sharing, and ensuring metadata consistency.

Looking ahead, integrating OGC standards, such as the SensorAPI for real-time data sharing, could further enhance interoperability of WOLL-type data. By testing these tools with Co-UDlabs datasets, we aim to validate their effectiveness and provide recommendations for broader adoption in the urban drainage community.

3.3.1. OGC Standards

In Deliverable 2.1, we identified the relevance of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards for improving semantic interoperability water quality monitoring projects. We discussed different Information Models, for example the SensorML, Observation & Measurements (O&M), and WaterML standards. These frameworks provide a structure for describing sensors, observations, and hydrological datasets. WaterML standards facilitate the exchange of hydrological data, water quality and timeseries data, while O&M offers a procedure for describing observations and their metadata.

The Information Model defines the data structures and relationships (e.g., how observations are represented or how sensor metadata is structured), while the Service Model focuses on how these data structures are accessed, shared, and used with web services. The Service Model contains the protocols that enable interoperable data exchange across systems.

Since D2.1, we found that the WaterML 2.0 standard is currently undergoing significant updates to enhance its alignment with emerging needs in water data management. For WaterML 2.0 Part 1 ('Timeseries'), revisions are being made to incorporate updates from ISO 19156:2023 (Observations, Measurements, and Samples - OMS). These updates integrate advancements from TimeSeries ML, a framework derived from Part 1, while also establishing best practices for ensuring compatibility with the SensorThings API. This alignment aims to modernize the handling and sharing of timeseries data in water management applications (Taylor et al., 2010).

Similarly, WaterML 2.0 Part 5 ('Water Quality') is being updated based on recommendations from the Water Quality Interoperability Experiment (IE). The IE has proposed creating a Best Practice document to guide implementation and has emphasize the need to adapt WaterML Part 1 to address shared quantities and harmonize standards across the framework (Cox & Simons, 2014).

The OGC is transitioning to align with modern web technologies and the growing demands of IoT applications. This shift, as confirmed during a meeting with Sylvain Griellet from BRGM and the Water4all project, reflects the movement from older, XML and SOAP-based Service Model standards like the Sensor Observation Service (SOS) to newer, JSON and REST-based Service Models such as the SensorThings API. The SensorThings API offers a more interoperable approach adjusted to the demands of current web applications.

This new standard introduces several advantages for UDS data. First, it provides enhanced data filtering capabilities, making it easier to perform complex queries. Additionally, SensorThings API supports both data reading and writing, allowing for dynamic, real-time updates within active systems (gamechanger for IoT deployments). Lastly, the simplified architecture reduces the learning curve for both IT professionals and UDS experts, enabling broader integration into existing workflows.

SensorThingsAPI deployment

While still in the adoption phase, SensorThings API is gaining traction with reference implementations (Kotsev et al., 2018) and adoption by governmental institutions. Based on these developments, we decided to transition from SOS to the SensorThings API, using the FROST server for implementation of WOLL-type data. This decision is driven by:

- The API's enhanced functionality for observation data filtering and real-time updates.
- Its alignment with modern web practices and IoT deployment needs.
- The potential to integrate updated WaterML standards, ensuring compatibility with the latest OGC advancements.

The WP2 is testing the SensorThingsAPI for data exchange, with the FROST Server serving as the implementation base for the Eawag UWO database. This move integrates a modern, RESTful, and JSON-based standard that aligns with the demands of IoT and water data management. The SensorThings API's compatibility with the Observations and Measurements (O&M) physical model supports the water quality data management and querying of relationships between entities (Figure 6) (Hertweck & Hellmund, 2019).

The deployment of the SensorThingsAPI focused on providing a local testing environment for standardized data sharing. The server was used to test the integration of the Urban Water Observatory (UWO) data, a rich dataset derived from spatially distributed sensors monitoring the urban water cycle in Fehrltorf (Blumensaat et al., 2024).

The UWO provides a unique dataset for urban water cycle monitoring, including spatially differentiated information on rainfall-driven processes, sewer flows, groundwater interactions, and water quality dynamics. Integrating this data into the SensorThings API allowed us to test its compatibility with OGC standards and its potential for real-time applications. Key benefits of this integration include:

Setting up the server locally involved configuring a PostgreSQL database with PostGIS support and deploying FROST-Server on an Apache Tomcat instance. This setup allowed us to simulate a production environment while adapting the system for the specific needs of the data. The steps we took for the deployment:

- Pre-installed PostgreSQL and PostGIS provided the spatial database capabilities needed for the server.
- Apache Tomcat was configured to host the FROST-Server, linking it to a PostgreSQL database. Resource definitions and connection pooling were set up in Tomcat's configuration files.
- After the deployment, we tested the system with UWO data, including rainfall, flow levels, and water quality measurements such as pH and turbidity. This testing helped validate the server ability to handle spatially distributed and high-frequency data streams.

This integration has several benefits, improving data interoperability by enabling UWO data to be shared with other systems and research projects through the OGC standards. Additionally, accessing the data via API provides valuable educational opportunities for researchers, allowing them to gain practical experience with modern monitoring and data sharing methods in real world scenarios.

Figure 6: Sketch of the SensorThingsAPI deployment for sharing of WOLL-type data from the RI UWO at Eawag. The image on top is the FROST server landing page. The bottom image shows the database storing the sensors data. (Source: Chavarría 2024)

Sharing urban drainage monitoring data using standardized tools like the SensorThings API can significantly boost WOLLs like FlowBru and the UWO, as well as the implementation of the UWWTD. Interoperability and standardization ensure that data from various sensors is shared in a consistent format, making it easy to integrate with other systems and platforms, e.g. open data portals. Second, real-time data access enables quick decision-making, particularly in urgent situations like flooding or water quality issues, which is already being implemented,

e.g. as EDM maps¹¹. Finally, using the SensorThings API makes it possible to directly reuse the data for regulatory compliance assessment.

3.4. Teaching, Dissemination and Promotion of Best Practices

Teaching and dissemination of the concepts and tools are vital to ensure that they are used in the UDS community. The ideal outcome would be that adopted of standardized practices and foster a collaborative community around urban drainage data management. Since the last deliverable, Co-UDlabs has presented a conference paper at ICUD, conducted a collaborative exchange at the University of La Coruña focused on OGC standards and DMP feedback, and contributed materials to the European Junior Scientist Workshop (EJSW) 2024. Additionally, Co-UDlabs is preparing an online workshop later in 2025 to explore reproducibility practices using Renku.

3.4.1. Reproducibility

We presented a conference paper at the International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD) 2024, the main triennial conference of the urban drainage community, where we explored how Renku, a platform designed for sustainable data science, could improve the reproducibility and provenance of data and models in urban drainage research (Figure 7) (Chavarría et al., 2024). Renku is compliant with the FAIR data principles, by supporting data and code sharing, tracking data provenance, and advancing transparency in workflows. In comparison to the EOSC, it is i) designed specifically to facilitate reproducible research by allowing researchers to track the entire lifecycle of their work and ii) is a much more integrated environment, where researchers can execute, visualize, and share their work (Roskar et al., 2023).

Figure 7: Presentation of *Improving the reproducibility and provenance of urban drainage data and models* in the ICUD conference 2024 (Source: Chavarría, 2024).

We show the benefits of the platform for FAIR data and reproducible research with three use cases:

1. **Identifying sediment deposits from temperature signals:** We tested Renku with an open dataset from the Co-UDlabs project, published on Zenodo. This dataset explores sediment deposit identification from difference in temperature signals without sediments (blue) and with sediments (red) as shown in Figure 8. It comprises CSV files containing cycle-based experiment data, sensor calibration information, and standard

¹¹ <https://www.thameswater.co.uk/edm-map>

methodologies, which are published under a CC-BY 4.0. Detailed metadata is available in a 40-page data collection report (Anta, Regueiro-Picallo, et al., 2022).

We developed a reproducible workflow in Renku by setting up a Python environment for data preparation, importing external data, and establishing workflows for data processing in Jupyter Notebooks. The reproducible workflow aligned closely with the original study results and also revealed a structural error in the data, emphasizing how reproducibility improves data reliability for validation by other users.

Original publication results

Reproducible workflow results

Figure 8: Comparison of results from the original publication and the reproducible workflow in Renku (Source: Chavarria, 2023)

- 2. Re-use data analysis:** The Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT) is a versatile suite for sensor calibration, data validation, and uncertainty assessment, aimed at improving urban drainage monitoring. It was developed by Co-UDlabs and available as a web app and downloadable executable. Some disadvantages of the webapp are the needed maintenance, static development, and the need for Matlab license. One of the functions the webapp offer is the Uncertainty Analysis Type B, also named LPU (Law of Propagation of Uncertainties) (Bertrand-Krajewski & Lepot, 2023).

Figure 9: Transitioning from the Matlab-based closed webapp to the Python-based open-source Renku project (Source: Chavarria, 2024)

We developed a project in Renku¹² using this particular feature of the UDMT (Figure 9), transforming first the Matlab code into Python. We identify several advantages of Renku, as being able to maintain processed data with method and parameter information, repeatability, preservation of the data lineage, visualization of data processes with knowledge graphs, and support of version control.

3. **Reproducible data science:** For this, we used the example of Automated Sewer Defect Detection developed by UoS (Figure 10). Integrating Co-UDlabs' deep-learning model for automated defect detection in CCTV sewer surveys into Renku¹³ was straight forward conceptually, but presented practical challenges. The computational demands of this pipeline exceeded the processing capabilities available in Renku's standard virtual machine configurations (Tait & Kazemi, 2023). Basically, this shortcoming demonstrates the limits of the public “flagship” deployment, RenkuLab, which is free for anyone to use. It does not question the general approach, because in theory, the UDS community could host their own RENKU instance with the computational resources required for specific applications.

While Renku provides computational resources suitable for many data science tasks, the free public deployment has natural limitations for resource-intensive operations. For instance, in our attempt to implement a deep-learning model for automated defect detection in CCTV sewer surveys, we encountered constraints due to Renkulab's computational capacity. The platform's current setup offers a maximum of 8GB RAM and 2 CPU cores (Figure 11), which may not be enough for heavy processing pipelines.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the Renku project Sewer Defects Classifier. The interface shows the preprocessing of the images using a workflow setup in a YAML file (Source: Chavarría, 2024)

¹² <https://renkulab.io/projects/alfredo.chavarria/coudlabs-udmt-typeb>

¹³ <https://renkulab.io/projects/gerome.meyer/sewer-defects-classifier-yolov8>

Session class				
Session requirements: 1 GB Disk (2 GB recommended)				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> xlarge	2 CPUs	8 GB RAM	10 GB Disk	0 GPUs
DEFAULT (paused after 2 hours of inactivity)				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> small	0.5 CPUs	1 GB RAM	10 GB Disk	0 GPUs
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> medium	1 CPUs	4 GB RAM	10 GB Disk	0 GPUs
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> large	2 CPUs	8 GB RAM	10 GB Disk	0 GPUs
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> xlarge	2 CPUs	8 GB RAM	10 GB Disk	0 GPUs

Figure 11: Screenshot of the RAM memory options offered in a Renkulab.io session

Renku is not designed as a primary data repository. Nevertheless, it supports integration with external storage solutions like AWS, Azure and, most importantly, Zenodo, allowing users to manage large datasets effectively. By default, data is stored using Git Large File Storage (LFS), but users can configure settings to accommodate different storage needs.

The platform supports various programming languages, including Python, R, and Julia. While MATLAB can be used within Renku, it requires appropriate licensing. Renku leverages Git for version control, ensuring that code changes are systematically tracked and managed.

With the development of Renku 2.0, there has been a strategic shift. The new version focuses on modular project configurations, allowing users to combine code repositories, data sources, and compute environments more flexibly. Despite these advancements, Renku 2.0 places less emphasis on tracking data provenance, a feature that was developed in the first version. For the TA researchers in urban drainage who rely on this functionality for reproducible workflows, this shift requires a reassessment of Renku suitability for the specific needs of reproducible research in Co-UDlabs and the UDS community. While Renku continues to offer the platform for reproducibility, alternative solutions may be required to maintain the same level of provenance tracking previously available (*Renku 2.0*, 2024).

Based on our results, it is clear that the Renkulab platform is not a universal solution, it has proven useful in creating reproducible workflows, especially in a field where data sharing and reuse can reduce costs and risks. Also, the integration with Zenodo communities, e.g. Co-UDlabs, works perfectly for data continuity. A broader adoption of Renku can facilitate a reproducible culture in urban drainage research.

3.4.2. Promoting use of standards: Mission to promote concepts and implementations at UDC

As part of the efforts of transfer knowledge in the project, we visited the University of La Coruña (UDC) to engage with their RI team. The visit provided an opportunity to share insights on OGC standards and collect feedback on our adjusted DMP framework. It was also a chance to learn about the challenges and strengths of UDC researchers approach to data management.

The visit opened with discussion sessions to explore UDC data management practices in detail. We discussed how data is stored in UDC and what platforms are used for collection and publication. These revealed the diversity in practices within their infrastructure, particularly regarding metadata management. While UDC has expertise in data collection in hydraulic lab and field experiments, there were opportunities to align their processes with broader standards to improve interoperability.

The DMP feedback session was particularly important. Researchers shared their views on the challenges they face with the current DMP framework, noting issues such as unclear guidance, the complexity of templates, and difficulties in meeting certain requirements. Tools like DMPOnline and UDMT were acknowledged as valuable but sometimes perceived as overly difficult or inflexible for practical application in their specific contexts. These insights reinforced the need for simpler tools, combined with training and clearer instructions. The session concluded with a review of our DMP template, providing important insights for new refinements.

As part of the visit itinerary, we included a presentation on the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards. The presentation was an overview of the OGC as a global organization working on interoperability in geospatial and sensor data. Topics covered included advanced frameworks like the Sensor Observation Service (SOS) and WaterML. The presentation highlighted the importance of harmonizing sensor data through OGC's dual approach of information models (defining data structures) and service models (how to interact with these structures). We showed practical examples on the use of OGC SOS for real-time data integration and WaterML 2.0 for hydrological data sharing. The session focusses on the application of these standards for Urban Drainage Systems (UDS), for managing sensor observations. An engaging aspect of the presentation was the discussion at the end where we talked about potential case studies.

Figure 12: Visit to the University of La Coruña. The photo on the left shows the OGC Standards presentation and discussion session. The photo on the right shows the STREET lab RI

This visit showed the value of direct engagement (Figure 12), as it was a productive exchange of ideas and perspectives, reaffirming that progress in harmonization requires collaboration. The feedback gathered during this visit started the changes to our DMP framework, developing a streamlined template. It also contributes to build the conference paper at ICUD, as we coordinate the use of TA projects like the research of Manuel Regueiro and the UDMT using the Renku platform.

In the future, promoting use of standards could readily be organized through the IWGDM, which organizes the UDM conference series and often calls for workshops at UDS conferences, which often target sharing best practices and providing hands-on training for researchers. Future workshops, such as those planned for UDM Innsbruck, will focus on the practical use of tools like SensorAPI and Renku.

3.4.3. OGC Interoperability Experiment (Hydrology Domain Working Group)

The Hydrology Domain Working Group (HDWG) is a collaborative initiative between the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO). It focuses on improving the way water information is described and shared. The group coordinates efforts with other Earth science working groups (Meteorology, Oceans, etc.) under the Earth System Science framework.

The Water Quality Interoperability Experiment (WQ IE) is a collaborative project designed to reinforce the WaterML 2.0 standard and test interoperability for water quality data systems using OGC service standards. The project builds upon the OGC standards baseline, and international best practices. As the WQ IE is concerned with introducing water quality monitoring into the OGC standards, it is very relevant for both Co-UDlabs laboratory data and WOLL-type of datasets.

The key goals of the WQ IE include developing a water quality observation model that uses existing OGC frameworks such as WaterML and SensorThings API. The experiment aims to identify appropriate APIs for water quality data exchange and test interoperability over different use cases. This process includes building consensus among stakeholders like the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA), to establish a unified approach for water quality data exchange (Grellet & Schaaf, 2024).

The work will be integrated in the WaterML 2.0 standard for water quality and will be mapped to existing organizational frameworks to test its applicability. These tests contribute to the development of an engineering report that outlines recommendations for implementing data exchange standards in the water quality domain. Additionally, the deployment of the WQ IE data model uses the SensorThings API and FROST Server Plugin, demonstrating how the model can be applied effectively.

Engaging with initiatives like the WQ IE allows us to test how our wastewater data model fits within existing standards and contributes to shaping them. Active participation ensures we stay involved in key decisions affecting water quality data and strengthens our understanding of interoperability in hydrology datasets and sensor networks.

The recommendation from the WP2 is that the UDS community, as well as the European Commission, actively participates in the Water Quality Interoperability Experiment (WQ IE) to ensure our data systems align with international best practices. Through this participation, Co-UDlabs contributes to refining WaterML standards and integrates the findings from WQ IE into our workflows.

4. Expected Outcome and Contribution to the Objectives of Co-UDlabs

The main task of Task 2.1 was to harmonize the data collected in the TA and JRAs of Co-UDlabs. As recommended by collaborators of the Water4all project, we structured our work into i) investigating suitable concepts, ii) developing suitable implementations in software and tools and iii) promoting and teaching these concepts with the UDLabs partners and in the UDS community. The main outcomes in these areas of work, and their contribution to the objectives are as follows:

4.1. Outcomes of Task 2.1.

4.1.1. Concept Development:

In this area, we focused on establishing a shared understanding of key terms, variables, and relationships in the field of urban drainage. This includes a comprehensive review of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) glossaries and

vocabularies, as well as an analysis of existing standards and ontologies like INSPIRE, OGC, ISO, SSN/SOSA, GEMET, and EnvThes. We leveraged existing work, ensuring compatibility with broader data management practices, and created a first version of a controlled vocabulary that serves as a reference for the Co-UDlabs project, e.g. or keywords on the Zenodo community, and future endeavors, such as the UDRAIN initiative (see Deliverable 1.2) .

This controlled vocabulary forms the basis for an ontology that supports data references and ensures project contributions align with future needs of the broader UDS community to collect data archives, e.g. for machine learning applications and knowledge extraction. Also, mapping project variables to established data models, was important to identify both the utility and limitations of current frameworks, such as the GWSW. Those variables which did not match highlight the need to expand existing frameworks to build in the flexibility to encompass unique data, which will ultimately contribute to a more robust data model for the RIs.

Also, we designed a collaborative activity in the IWGDM to ensure that experts join forces to continue the development of the data standards within the community after the end of Co-UDLabs.

4.1.2. Implementation:

To put some of the developed concepts into practice, we focused on developing or using appropriate tools and technologies. First, we implemented our data sharing in the Zenodo platforms and have been actively exploring the use of online platforms for reproducible workflows, such as Renku. For semantic interoperability in UDS projects, we have been implementing OGC standards, including the SensorThings API and WaterML, to efficiently share the data from the Eawag Research Infrastructure Urban Water Observatory (UWO), including Metadata. The project has transitioned from older standards like SOS to the newer SensorThings API due to its enhanced functionality for real-time updates, its alignment with modern web practices, and its compatibility with updated WaterML standards. Testing these tools with real datasets, like data from the UWO, is critical for validating their effectiveness and making recommendations to the broader urban drainage community for adoption.

4.1.3. Teaching:

To ensure that the implementations are used, we also educated the researchers and practitioners on the harmonisation concepts about the tools and best practices developed during the project.

Specifically, Co-UDlabs has been actively disseminating its findings through presentations at conferences like ICUD and workshops, such as the EJSW. Sharing best practices and providing hands-on training for the UDS community on these tools will continue in the next months, with specific workshops planned for events like the Urban Drainage Modelling conference in Innsbruck 2025. In the Task2.1 we also explored and demonstrated the use of Renku for improving the reproducibility and provenance of data and models in urban drainage research by using it to reproduce results from previous studies, re-use existing data and models, and test the application of deep learning models for sewer defect detection developed in WP7.

4.2. Contribution to the Objective of Co-UDLabs

The outcomes of Task 2.1 directly contribute to the three objectives of the Co-UDlabs project in the following ways.

4.2.1. Objective 1: Foster a culture of co-operation between RIs and the urban drainage community

The outcomes of Task 2.1, particularly the development of a shared vocabulary, frameworks, and ontologies, directly contribute to this objective by creating a common language and standard for the urban drainage community. By harmonising data and promoting interoperability, Task 2.1 facilitates collaboration across multiple

research infrastructures (RIs) and institutions. The tools and protocols developed, such as the adoption of OGC standards and the promotion of platforms like Zenodo and Renku, encourage a more open and efficient research environment. These efforts help break down silos, foster cooperation, and ensure that researchers from various sectors and countries can effectively collaborate on shared challenges in urban drainage.

4.2.2. Objective 2: Provide research infrastructure for breakthrough research and innovation

Through Task 2.1, Co-UDlabs strengthens the Transnational Access activities by developing a robust framework for data harmonisation and reuse, specifically the knowledge-based research infrastructure, e.g. data models and exchange formats. By ensuring data interoperability and creating platforms for reproducible workflows, Task 2.1 lays the foundation for data collections, which will pave the way for EU data spaces. Large corpuses of structured, annotated and possibly curated datasets will make it possible to apply machine learning, e.g. like anomaly detection or data augmentation algorithms to ensure good data quality and predictive modelling. Figuratively speaking, applications like ChatGPT are not possible today, because a common “language and structure” for the diverse datasets is still missing. Thus, promoting and showcasing international standards, such as the SensorThings API for real-time data sharing, directly supports the capacity for transformative engineering and research.

4.2.3. Objective 3: Enlarge and strengthen the quality and quantity of services offered by Co-UDlabs

Task 2.1's outcomes are instrumental in expanding and enhancing digital water data analysis tools in the UDS community, thereby directly contributing to this objective. By defining FAIR standards, platforms for data sharing, and the necessary keywords to find the data later, the task ensures that Co-UDlabs can provide high-quality, accessible, and interoperable data for the urban drainage sector. The adoption of digital tools like Renku for reproducible workflows and the implementation of OGC standards for real-time data integration enhance Co-UDlabs' capabilities in digital water data analysis. These improvements increase the quality and quantity of services the RIs can offer at the European level, making data and tools more accessible to a broader range of researchers and practitioners alike.

The achieved and anticipated outcomes have substantial socio-environmental implications and align with broader EU policies. Recognizing technologies like 'Technologies (such as Big data)' as key to a Water Smart Society, as outlined in the Water Europe platform's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SIRA)¹⁴, highlights this alignment. Truly FAIR data form the backbone of the European Open Science Cloud¹⁵ and it's goal for seamless, standardized data access, advancing EU research objectives as well as the future EU Data spaces with their data valuation focus¹⁶. These efforts contribute to Horizon Europe's vision of a sustainable, equitable, and prosperous future, addressing climate change, supporting Sustainable Development Goals, and enhancing the EU's competitiveness and growth.

¹⁴ <https://watereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Water-Europe-SIRA.pdf>

¹⁵ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en#what-the-european-open-science-cloud-is

¹⁶ <https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/datastories/when-open-data-meets-data-spaces>

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Appendix

TA-JRA variables, sensors, units and references

No.	Variable	Unit	Sensor or Lab method	Reference	RI
1	Ammonium Nitrogen	mg/L	Hyperspectral imaging	EnvThes	HALL
2	Biomass		Lab analysis	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	BLOCK
3	Cell counts	Number	Flow Cytometry	[undetermined]	ANNULAR
4	Chemical Oxygen Demand	mg/L	Hyperspectral imaging	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
5	Chemical Oxygen Demand	mg/L	Wastewater Sample Analysis	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
6	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
7	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	ANNULAR
8	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BURIED
9	Conductivity	mS/cm	Dielectric Conductivity Sensors	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
10	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	STREET
11	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	STREET
12	Conductivity	mS/cm	Conductivity Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BLOCK
13	CRISPR-Cas	DNA or RNA sequences	Molecular Method	GEMET;EnvThes	ANNULAR
14	Density	kg/m ³	Sediment Analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
15	Density	kg/m ³	Sediment Analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
16	Density	kg/m ³	Sediment Analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	ANNULAR
17	Density	kg/m ³	Sediment analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	BLOCK
18	Depth	mm	Depth Sensor	EN 16323;EnvThes	ANNULAR
19	Depth	mm	Water depth sensor	EN 16323;EnvThes	BLOCK
20	Digital PCR	target molecules per microliter (copies/μL)	Molecular Method	EN 16323;EnvThes	ANNULAR
21	Dissolved Oxygen	mg/L	Dissolved Oxygen Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	ANNULAR
22	DOC	mg/L	Lab analysis		STREET
23	Fine/coarse-grained, mineral substances		Retention Testing		IKT TEST
24	Flow Depths	mm	Depth Sensor	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
25	Flow pressure	mA	Pressure Sensor	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
26	Flow pressure	mA	Pressure Sensor	EnvThes	BURIED
27	Flow Rate	L/s	Level Sensor	EN 16323	BENS
28	Flow Rate	L/s	Flow Meter	EN 16323	BENS

29	Flow Rate	L/s	Ultrasonic Flow Transducer	EN 16323	BENS
30	Flow Rate	m3/s	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler	EN 16323	ANNULAR
31	Flow Rate	L/s	Flow Meter	EN 16323	BURIED
32	Flow Rate	L/s	Calibrated Weirs	EN 16323	BURIED
33	Flow Rate	L/s	Flow Meter	EN 16323	BURIED
34	Flow Rate	L/s	Correlation Wedge Sensors	EN 16323	UWO
35	Flow Rate	L/s	Non-Contact Radar Flow Meters	EN 16323	UWO
36	Flow Rate	L/s	Flow Meter	EN 16323	IKT LTF
37	Flow Rate	L/s	Pump	EN 16323	IKT LTF
38	Flow Rate	L/s	Flow Meter	EN 16323	IKT TEST
39	Flow rate	L/s	Flow Sensor	EN 16323	STREET
40	Flow rate	L/s	Flowmeter	EN 16323	STREET
41	Flow rate	L/s	Flow sensor	EN 16323	BLOCK
42	Flow rate	L/s	Flow sensor	EN 16323	BLOCK
43	Flow rate	L/s	Flowmeter	EN 16323	RTC
44	Flow rate	L/s	Flow sensor	EN 16323	RTC
45	Flow velocity	m/s	Particle Image Tomography	EnvThes	ANNULAR
46	Flow velocity	m/s	Image based particle tracking	EnvThes	ANNULAR
47	Flow velocity	m/s	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler	EnvThes	BURIED
48	Flow velocity	m/s	Laser Doppler Velocimetry	EnvThes	BURIED
49	Flow velocity	m/s	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler	EnvThes	BURIED
50	Humidity	m3/m3	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
51	images output		Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy		ANNULAR
52	images output		Scanning Electron Microscopy		ANNULAR
53	images output		Microscopy and imaging facilities		ANNULAR
54	images output		Multispectral and Hyperspectral Sensors		HALL
55	MCPA		LC/MS-MS		STREET
56	Mean grain size	mm	Sediment Analysis		BENS
57	Mean grain size	mm	Sediment Analysis		ANNULAR
58	Mean grain size	mm	PSD Analysis		STREET
59	Metagenomics	DNA or RNA sequences	Molecular Method		ANNULAR
60	Microbial concentrations		Lab analysis		BLOCK

61	Microbiological analysis		Water and Soil Sample Analysis	GEMET	ANNULAR
62	Mineral oil hydrocarbons		Retention Testing	GEMET	IKT TEST
63	Moisture content	%	Sediment Analysis	EnvThes	HALL
64	Moisture content	%	Sediment Analysis	EnvThes	BENS
65	Moisture content	%	Environmental Sensor	EnvThes	STREET
66	Organic matter	%	Sediment Analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
67	Organic matter	%	Sediment Analysis	GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
68	Orthophosphate Phosphorus	mg/L	Lagrangian Sensor Platform	GEMET	HALL
69	pH	ph	pH Sensor	EnvThes	ANNULAR
70	pH	ph	ph Sensor	EnvThes	STREET
71	pH	ph	ph Sensor	EnvThes	BLOCK
72	Physicalchemical analysis		Water and Soil Sample Analysis		ANNULAR
73	Polyethylene and polystyrene		Retention Testing		IKT TEST
74	Porosity	ϕ	Sediment Analysis	EnvThes	BENS
75	Pressure	bar	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
76	Pressure	Bar	Pressure Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	IKT LTF
77	q-PCR	cycle threshold (Ct)	Molecular Method		ANNULAR
78	Quantities and particle sizes of sediments	mm	Weighing Scale		BURIED
79	Rainfall	mm/h	Rain Gauge	DIN 752 2008;EnvThes	UWO
80	Rainfall	mm/h	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	DIN 752 2008;EnvThes	UWO
81	Rainfall	mm/h	Rain gauge	DIN 752 2008;EnvThes	STREET
82	Rainfall	mm/h	Rain gauge	DIN 752 2008;EnvThes	BLOCK
83	Rainfall		Rain gauge	DIN 752 2008;EnvThes	STREET
84	Rainfall duration		Rain gauge		STREET
85	Ryegrass germination		Image analysis		BLOCK
86	Ryegrass growth Rate		Image analysis		BLOCK
87	Sediment concentration		Sediment analysis	EnvThes	STREET
88	Simulation damages	[undetermined]	CCTV	GWSW	IKT LTF
89	Solar radiation	W/m2	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
90	Solute concentration	mg/L	Fluorometer	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
91	Solute concentration	mg/L	Planar Concentration Analysis System	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
92	Solute concentration	mg/L	Solute Concentration Sensor	EnvThes	BURIED
93	Strain	micrometer/m	Strain Gauges		IKT LTF

94	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
95	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	ANNULAR
96	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BURIED
97	Temperature	Celsius	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
98	Temperature	Celsius	Dual Sensors	GEMET;EnvThes	UWO
99	Temperature	Celsius	Dynamic Heat Pulse System	GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
100	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
101	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	STREET
102	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	BLOCK
103	Temperature	Celsius	Temperature Sensor	GEMET;EnvThes	STREET
104	Thermal conductivity	W/m/Celsius	Sediment Analysis	Thermopedia	HALL
105	Thermal conductivity	W/m/C	Sediment Analysis	Thermopedia	ANNULAR
106	Titanium		ICP/MS	GEMET	STREET
107	Total Nitrogen	mg/L	Wastewater Sample Analysis	EN 16323;EnvThes	BENS
108	Total Phosphorus	mg/L	Wastewater Sample Analysis	EN 16323;EnvThes	BENS
109	Total Solids	g/Kg	Wastewater Sample Analysis	EN 16323	BENS
110	Total Suspended Solids	mg/L	Wastewater Sample Analysis	EN 16323	BENS
111	Turbidity	NTU	Turbidity Sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	BENS
112	Turbidity	NTU	Ultrasonic Profilers	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
113	Turbidity	NTU	Turbidity Sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes	HALL
114	UV light intensity		UV Light meter		STREET
115	Velocity	m/s	Velocity Profiler	EnvThes	BENS
116	Velocity	L/s	Particle Image Velocimetry	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
117	Velocity	L/s	Flow Meter	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
118	Velocity	L/s	Particle Image Velocimetry	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
119	Velocity	L/s	Laser Doppler Velocimetry	EnvThes	A/B FLUME
120	Velocity	L/s	Particle Image Velocimetry	EnvThes	ANNULAR
121	Velocity	L/s	Particle Image Velocimetry	EnvThes	BURIED
122	Velocity	m/s	Ultrasonic Profilers	EnvThes	HALL
123	Velocity	m/s	UDV profiler	EnvThes	BLOCK
124	Velocity	m/s	PTV	EnvThes	BLOCK
125	Velocity	m/s	Particle Image Velocimetry	EnvThes	RTC
126	Volumetric heat capacity	J/m3/Celsius	Sediment Analysis		HALL
127	Volumetric heat capacity	J/m3/C	Sediment Analysis		ANNULAR

128	Volumetric moisture content	m3/m3	Sediment Analysis	GEMET	HALL
129	Waste water (synthetic)		Simulation	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	IKT TEST
130	Water leak	[undetermined]	Leak Tightness Testing	GWSW	IKT LTF
131	Water level	mm	Level Sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	BENS
132	Water level	mm	Computer Vision System	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	BENS
133	Water level	m	Water Level Wave Probes	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	BURIED
134	Water level	m	Overflow Structure Instrumentation	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	UWO
135	Water level	m3/m3	Pressure Sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	IKT TEST
136	Water level	L	Weighing Scale	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	IKT TEST
137	Water level	L	Depth sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	STREET
138	Water level		Radar sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	RTC
139	Water level		Conductance probes	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	RTC
140	Water level		Water level sensor	EN 16323;GEMET;EnvThes;GWSW	RTC
141	Water volume		Flow sensor	EN 16323	STREET
142	Water weight		Weighing Scale	GEMET;EnvThes	STREET
143	Wind	m/s	Multi-Parameter Weather Station	EnvThes	UWO
144	[undetermined]	[undetermined]	Wastewater Sample Analysis	[undetermined]	BENS